

X-Ray diffraction studies of Schiff base 4-[2'-hydroxysalicylidene 5'-(2''-thiazolyazo)]nitrobenzene

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Abstract : X-Ray diffraction studies have been carried out for 4-[2'-hydroxysalicylidene 5'-(2''-thiazolyazo)]nitrobenzene. This ligand is synthesized and purified by condensing 5-(2'-thiazolyazo)salicylaldehyde and *p*-nitroaniline. The structure of compound is found to be tetragonal belonging to non-primitive system. The strain broadening effects are also examined and discussed.

Keywords : Azo Schiff base, X-ray diffraction, *p*-nitroaniline.

Introduction

Schiff base of thiazole compounds having azo and azomethine groups are known to possess bacteriostatic, anticancerous, and other biochemical activities¹⁻⁵. In such studies, aniline has been widely used as a precursor for the preparation of bidentate Schiff bases, by simple condensation of their primary amino group with the carbonyl compounds. Bidentate and tridentate Schiff bases also can be synthesized by using azo-substituted salicylaldehyde and anilines. In order to characterize and elucidate structural details, we have studied the solid state properties which can be used for modeling purposes. In this communication, we report X-ray diffraction properties of 4-[2'-hydroxysalicylidene 5'-(2''-thiazolyazo)]-nitrobenzene compound which has been found to be a good complexing compound.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents used were of A.R. grade. 5-(2'-Thiazolyazo)salicylaldehyde was prepared following a reported method⁶. The Schiff base ligand was synthesized by dissolving 5-(2'-thiazolyazo)salicylaldehyde (0.01 mole) in 50 ml ethanol, to this, a solution of *p*-nitroaniline (0.01 mole) in 15 ml ethanol was added and resulting mixture was refluxed for three hours on water bath. After cooling, the solution was poured in ice-cold water, the separated solid was filtered, dried and purified by repetitive recrystallisation from ethanol and dried in air. The purity was checked by thin layer chro-

matography (TLC).

The result with respect to elemental analysis, colour, yield, melting point etc. are as follows : Red brown, yield 72%, m.p. 158 °C, IR : 1625 ν (C=N), 1545 ν (N=N), 1295 cm^{-1} ν (C-O) (Found : C, 54.38; H, 3.13; N, 19.81; S, 9.07. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_5\text{O}_3\text{S}$: C, 54.50; H, 3.19; N, 19.22, S, 9.18%).

Structure of the ligand was tentatively fixed as given in Fig. 1 on the basis of elemental analysis, IR, UV and ¹H NMR spectral studies.

The XRD pattern of the ligand was recorded in the range 2 θ from 0° to 80° on Philips PW 3710 Diffractometer attached to digitized computer along with graphical assembly in which CuK α radiation source is connected with the tube Cu-Ni 25 kV/20 mA.

Fig. 1. Structure of ligand 4-[2'-hydroxysalicylidene 5'-(2''-thiazolyazo)]nitrobenzene.

Results and discussion

The X-ray diffraction spectrum of the Schiff base 4-[2'-hydroxysalicylidene 5'-(2''-thiazolyazo)]nitrobenzene

Table 1. Powder X-ray diffraction data of 4-[2'-hydroxysalicylidene 5'-(2''-thiazolylazo)]nitrobenzene

Peak no	2 θ (deg)	d_{obs} (Å)	d_{cal} (Å)	Q_{obs}	Q_{cal}	$h k l$	RI (%)
1	9.14	9.6672	9.6672	0.0107	0.0107	0 0 1	31.0
2	14.30	6.0415	6.1906	0.0260	0.0273	2 1 0	8.8
3	16.19	5.5370	5.4709	0.0334	0.0326	2 0 1	100
4	17.90	4.8336	4.9511	0.0407	0.0428	0 0 2	13.4
5	18.48	4.7763	4.7970	0.0434	0.0438	2 2 0	19.5
6	20.64	4.3129	4.3006	0.0540	0.0537	1 1 2	10.0
7	23.36	3.7743	3.8048	0.0690	0.0701	2 1 2	9.4
8	24.20	3.7468	3.6746	0.0740	0.0712	3 1 2	8.6
9	25.25	3.4936	3.5241	0.0805	0.0819	3 2 1	13.0
10	26.25	3.3974	3.3965	0.0866	0.0866	2 2 2	20.4
11	28.22	3.1842	3.1603	0.1001	0.0986	3 3 0	8.5
12	30.27	2.9613	2.9496	0.1149	0.1140	3 2 2	96.0
13	31.99	2.7685	2.7953	0.1279	0.1276	4 0 2	8.7
14	42.32	2.1360	2.1338	0.2196	0.2191	6 2 0	11.3
15	53.72	1.7026	1.7047	0.3441	0.3452	6 5 1	3.0

is shown in Fig. 2. The presence of even sharp single reflection in XRD pattern indicates the formation of a single-phase compound. The XRD pattern shows fifteen reflection between the range of 2θ from 0° and 80° with maxima at $2\theta = 16.19^\circ$ corresponding to a value of $d = 5.5370 \text{ \AA}$.

The 2θ values for prominent peaks are listed in Table 1. All main peaks have been indexed by using appropriate methodology and use of computer program (Powdmult, Version 2.3). The indexing is confirmed on the basis of correction obtained between observed and calculated d and Q values based on characteristics of symmetry consideration. The method also yielded hkl (miller indices) values. The relative intensities corresponding to the prominent peaks have been also calculated (Table 1).

Assuming the ligand as a tetragonal system, the unit

Fig. 2. X-Ray diffractogram of ligand.

cell lattice parameters⁷ are found to be $a = b = 13.5093 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 9.6672 \text{ \AA}$, respectively, while the cell volume is 1764.27 \AA^3 . The unit cell parameters were refined by weight fraction method. Such refined parameters were used for finding out space group and Laue group from International Tables of Crystallography⁸. In conjugation with such cell parameters the condition, such as $a = b \neq c$ and $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$ required for the sample to be tetragonal were tested and found to be in good agreement^{9,10}. The standard deviation Q 's were of the order of 10^{-4} . On the basis of the magnitude of deviation, it can be said that, the way of processing adopted for evaluation of cell parameters, is appropriate, indicating the non-primitive tetragonal structure for the compound¹¹.

The experimental value of density (ρ) has been calculated by using specific gravity method. The number of atoms per unit cell n , was calculated by using the equation :

$$n = \rho NV/M$$

where ρ is density, M is the molecular weight, V the unit cell volume and N is the Avogadro number. With this n value, the theoretical density was calculated and found to be in good agreement with the experimental value. The other parameters such as pore fraction, packing fraction, particle size, and radius of atom were then calculated. All these values are tabulated in Table 2.

The particle size (t) of the sample was calculated by

Table 2. X-Ray parameters of 4-[2'-hydroxysalicylidene 5'-(2''-thiazolylazo)]nitrobenzene

Structure	Tetragonal
Space group	P_4/mmm
Laue group	4/m
Point group	4/mmm
Symmetry of lattice	Non primitive
Lattice parameters	$a = b = 13.5093 \text{ \AA}$ $c = 9.6672 \text{ \AA}$
Volume of unit cell	1764.27 \AA^3
Packing fraction	47.49%
Density ρ (Experimental)	0.665 g/cc
(Theoretical)	0.651 g/cc
Pore fraction	30.08%
Thickness of particle	255.71 \AA

using an equation

$$t = 0.9 \lambda / B \cos \theta.$$

The parameters can distinguish between natural particle size and particle size due to broadening effect¹². This was done by calculating full width at half maximum (B) corresponding to its Bragg's 2θ values. The nature and behavior of these values for the present ligand are shown graphically in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Analysis of homogeneity.

A plot of $B \cos \theta$ versus $\sin \theta$ was found to be a straight line parallel to X axis, indicating an absence of

any strains caused by homogeneous lattice distortion and compositional fluctuations. Hence, present ligand seems to be homogeneous with respect to the particle size distribution.

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References

1. R. Price, in "Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry", eds. G. Wilkinson, R. D. Ghildard and C. T. Stears, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1987, Vol. 6.
2. N. L. Wengnack, H. M. Hoard and F. Rusnak, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **121**, 9748.
3. P. P. Hankare, R. K. Patil, S. S. Chavan, A. H. Jagtap and B. S. Battase, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1328.
4. M. R. Maurya, P. J. Bahad, A. V. Pardhi and A. S. Aswar, *Bioinorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2000, **10**, 2243.
5. P. C. Joshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 467.
6. P. P. Hankare, L. V. Gavali and S. S. Chavan, *Indian J. Phys.*, 2002, **76A**, 587.
7. P. Lingaiah, T. Ramkrishnarao and L. Sirdeshmukh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 826.
8. J. D. H. Donnay and Haker Dai, "Tables of Space and Group Criteria Crytallographiques", *Naturalist Canadian* 67, 1940, p. 33 and 160.
9. B. D. Cullity, "Element of X-Ray Diffraction", Wesley, London, 1959.
10. F. M. Henry, H. Lipson and W. A. Wooster, "Interpretation of X-Ray Diffraction Photographs", 1951, p. 81.
11. A. Z. Sami and Jejurkar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, **34**, 241.
12. S. Peiser, H. P. Rooksby and A. J. C. Wilson, "X-Ray Diffraction by Polycrystalline Materials", Institute of Physics, London, 1955, 344.